
ANTI-OPTIMIZATION BASED UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS FOR COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Keywords: Anti-optimization, laminated composites, interval-based uncertainty analysis, convex hull

Abstract. *Composite materials are used in diverse engineering applications and are widely applied in high-performance tasks such as in aircraft, automobiles and in the military industry. Over the past few decades, many researchers studied the behavior of these materials, promoting big advances in the area. Although great progress has been achieved, variability from experimental data obtained for, a priori, and nominally identical specimens is still not well explained. Random and epistemic uncertainties are often pointed as the main causes of this divergence. This work presents an algorithm based on interval analysis to quantify uncertainties in composite laminates. The α -cut procedures are used to take into account various uncertainties present in the material, geometry, or external loading. The solutions found in this work are compared with the robust Monte Carlo method, showing that the algorithm presented here finds wider intervals than those found by Monte Carlo, indicating a more precise analysis.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The uncertainty present in composite materials can be a big issue in the design and manufacture phases of the layers that compose the final structure. These uncertainties can be inserted into the system in a number of ways, such as through temperature sensitivity, hygroscopic phenomena, and the own manufacturing process. Even the standardized tests used to characterize the elastic properties of the composite material have some degree of uncertainty as explained by [1]. The lack of accurate material properties (required in order to predict failure mechanisms, dynamic behavior and deformation) may lead to excessively conservative designs [3, 6].

According to [2], current approaches to the problem of uncertainty are divided into two major groups: possibilistic modeling of uncertainty and probabilistic modeling of uncertainty. The probabilistic approach requires knowing the probabilistic distribution of the uncertainties and the correlation between variables, which is not normally known in practice. The possibilistic approach, on the other hand, only requires the range of uncertainty possibilities, which is a common data. The interval analysis used in this work fits the possibility approach. An extensive bibliography exists in quantifying these uncertainties like those discussed in [3]. In this paper, the developed algorithm is based on the α -cut concept and convex hull from the quick hull algorithm [4] as explained in [5].

For the Interval Approach used in the algorithm framework of the present work, the measure of confidence on the uncertainty level of variables can be associated to an ALPHA-cut level (Figure 1(b)), a single value that varies from 0 to 1 (where 0 is the maximum uncertainty in the interval limit and 1 being complete confidence and thus, no uncertainty at all).

Several simplified methods can be used to evaluate the propagation of these uncertainties intervals, such as gradient-based methods and arithmetic intervals, but none of them are sufficiently accurate for all levels of uncertainty. For this reason, some more elaborated approaches must be used, such as the anti-optimization. For the anti-optimization approach, an optimization algorithm is used to

find the limits of the output variables that represent the behavior of the system based on combinations of the uncertain variables. The Monte Carlo approach is also useful in this concern, being a very robust solution to the uncertainty propagation problem. As explained in [3], the Monte Carlo simulation technique in conjunction with the finite element (FE) method is found to be widely used for quantifying uncertainties of laminated composite structures, as it is done in [6]. The comparison between the Monte Carlo and the anti-optimization approach is explored later in this work, where it is shown that Monte Carlo is not the best choice regarding performance and efficiency.

1.1. Uncertainty propagation and anti-optimization

Assume a system with the input vector ${}^m\mathbf{X} = ({}^m x_1, {}^m x_2, \dots, {}^m x_{ni})^T$, where ni is the number of input variables, m means “measured”, and an output vector as ${}^m\mathbf{Z} = ({}^m z_1, {}^m z_2, \dots, {}^m z_{no})^T$, where no is the number of output variables. Let’s assume a number of samples of each one of the input vectors (called realizations) ${}^m_1\mathbf{X}, {}^m_2\mathbf{X}, \dots, {}^m_{ns}\mathbf{X}$ and the corresponding output vectors ${}^m_1\mathbf{Z}, {}^m_2\mathbf{Z}, \dots, {}^m_{ns}\mathbf{Z}$, where ns means the number of samples. Furthermore, let’s assume a numerical model of the system with the same measured inputs ${}^m\mathbf{X} = ({}^m x_1, {}^m x_2, \dots, {}^m x_{ni})^T$, adjustable model’s parameters vector $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{np})^T$, with np representing the number of parameters and predicted vector outputs ${}^p\mathbf{Z} = ({}^p z_1, {}^p z_2, \dots, {}^p z_{no})^T = f({}^m\mathbf{X}, \boldsymbol{\theta})$. Related to the output vector, it is easy to obtain their upper and lower bounds based on the values from all realizations. These output intervals vector may be put together in a two-column vector representation as:

$$[{}^m\mathbf{z}, {}^m\bar{\mathbf{z}}] = [\min_{i=1, \dots, ns}({}^m_i\mathbf{z}) \max_{i=1, \dots, ns}({}^m_i\mathbf{z})] \quad (1)$$

This represents a measure of the model’s output uncertainty or dispersion. The same can be stated for the predicted output vector (from the numerical model) and the measured input vector:

$$[{}^m\mathbf{X}, {}^m\bar{\mathbf{X}}] = [\min_{i=1, \dots, ns}({}^m_i\mathbf{X}) \max_{i=1, \dots, ns}({}^m_i\mathbf{X})] \quad (2)$$

$$[\boldsymbol{\theta}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}] = [\min_{i=1, \dots, np}(\theta_i) \max_{i=1, \dots, np}(\theta_i)] \quad (3)$$

$$[{}^p\mathbf{z}, {}^p\bar{\mathbf{z}}] = f([{}^m\mathbf{X}, {}^m\bar{\mathbf{X}}], [\boldsymbol{\theta}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]) = [\min_{i=1, \dots, ns}({}^p_i\mathbf{z}([\boldsymbol{\theta}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}])) \max_{i=1, \dots, ns}({}^p_i\mathbf{z}([\boldsymbol{\theta}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]))] \quad (4)$$

A very common question is: What are the output intervals $[{}^p\mathbf{z}, {}^p\bar{\mathbf{z}}]$ for a given set of measured input intervals $[{}^m\mathbf{X}, {}^m\bar{\mathbf{X}}]$ and parameters intervals $[\boldsymbol{\theta}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]$? This may be thought of as finding the variability of the response of the system (upper and lower bounds of the output behavior). This also can be understood as an uncertainty propagation in terms of intervals, since the uncertainty of the inputs and parameters will be propagated to the outputs. This is as a double optimization (minimization and maximization, also known as anti-optimization) in each of the hypervolume quadrants (2^{no}) to find the best input ${}^m\mathbf{X}^*$ and parameter values $\boldsymbol{\theta}^*$ that maximizes (or minimizes) the output norm $\|{}^p\mathbf{z}\|_2$ and that complies with the bounded intervals. The final output intervals will be the minimum and maximum of each variable for all hyper-quadrants. Mathematically, this can be stated as:

At each hyper quadrant, Find $\mathbf{X}^*, \boldsymbol{\theta}^*$ that minimizes and maximizes $\|\mathbf{z}^*\|_2$

$$\text{Subject to : } \mathbf{X}^* \in [{}^m\mathbf{X}, {}^m\bar{\mathbf{X}}], \boldsymbol{\theta}^* \in [\boldsymbol{\theta}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}] \text{ and } [{}^p\mathbf{z}, {}^p\bar{\mathbf{z}}] = [\min_{\text{over all quadrants}}(\mathbf{z}^*) \max_{\text{over all quadrants}}(\mathbf{z}^*)] \quad (5)$$

In this case, where a double optimization happens, the number of design variables is $(ni+np)$. A block diagram can be sketched in this sense, as represented in Figure 1(a).

The interval upper and lower values form a cloud in the hyperspace and, once obtained, a convenient way to visualize in constructing a convex hull, which is the smallest convex set that contains and encompasses the set of points. This convex hull can also be constructed, if Monte Carlo Methods are used, for the random points obtained by the simulations.

Figure 1 –(a) Interval uncertainty propagation. (b) Linear approximation of Gaussian distribution forx by a triangular fuzzy-set, with uncertain intervals and α -cuts.

2. COMPOSITE MATERIAL

Laminated composite structures can be challenging to manufacture accurately according to its exact design specifications because of the inherent complexity present in such materials. As a result, undesirable and unavoidable uncertainties arise in composite manufacturing, such as intra-laminate voids, incomplete curing of the resin, excess resin between plies, porosity, excess matrix voids, variations in ply thickness and fiber parameters, all those making the overall behavior prediction of such materials difficult [3,6]. The lack of precise tools to evaluate the propagation of these uncertainties may lead to overly conservative or unsafe designs, with a more expensive and less effective final product.

In this study, only mass density, ply angle orientation and Elastic modulus values will be considered with uncertain values since those are the most important source of the variability described in the literature [3].

2.1. Equations for dynamic vibrations of laminated plates

The differential equations for a laminated plate can be derived from analyzing Figure 2, where a force diagram is depicted (comma represents the corresponding partial derivatives).

Figure 2– Force diagram at the middle surface of a laminated plate.

By the resulting forces in x and y directions, we find (i) $N_{x,x} + N_{xy,x} = 0$ and (ii) $N_{y,y} + N_{xy,y} = 0$. Considering the inertia force (density ρ and height h) and the forces in the z -direction, one finds the equilibrium equation $Q_{x,x} + Q_{y,y} + N_x w_{,xx} + 2N_{xy} w_{,xy} + N_y w_{,yy} - \rho h w_{,tt} = 0$. For the moment equations and neglecting the third-order terms, one finds $M_{x,x} + M_{xy,y} = Q_x$ and $M_{y,y} + M_{xy,x} = Q_y$ that results in (iii) $M_{x,xx} + 2M_{xy,yx} + M_{y,yy} + N_x w_{,xx} + 2N_{xy} w_{,xy} + N_y w_{,yy} - \rho h w_{,tt} = 0$. This forms a set of three differential equations of motion. For a laminated plate, the constitutive relations for stress/strains at the local coordinate system for laminate k at height z is (assuming First-Order Shear Deformation Theory, FSDT):

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix}_k \left(\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} + z \begin{Bmatrix} k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \right) \quad (6)$$

and the internal forces evaluated as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \int_{-t/2}^{+t/2} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}_k dz \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{Bmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \int_{-t/2}^{+t/2} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}_k z dz \quad (7)$$

and applying Equation (6), one recovers:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{A}_{ij} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} + \mathbf{B}_{ij} \begin{Bmatrix} k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{Bmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{B}_{ij} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} + \mathbf{D}_{ij} \begin{Bmatrix} k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The matrices \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{D} are evaluated as usual, along each ply, as $\mathbf{A}_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n \kappa (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k - z_{k-1})$, $\mathbf{B}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2)$ and $\mathbf{D}_{ij} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^n (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3)$ and $\kappa = 5/6$. Based on the Classical Laminated Theory, taking the strain displacement relationship, one finds:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} = +\mathbf{B}_{ij} \begin{Bmatrix} u_x \\ v_y \\ u_y + v_x \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{Bmatrix} k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} -w_{,xx} \\ -w_{,yy} \\ -2w_{,xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

and finally, the set of the three differential equations, taking into consideration Equation (8) results in:

$$\begin{aligned} & A_{11}u_{,xx} + 2A_{16}u_{,xy} + A_{66}u_{,yy} + A_{16}v_{,xx} + (A_{11} + A_{66})v_{,xy} + A_{26}v_{,yy} - B_{11}w_{,xxx} - 3B_{16}w_{,xxy} \\ & \quad - (B_{12} + 2B_{66})w_{,xyy} - B_{26}w_{,yyy} = 0 \\ & A_{16}u_{,xx} + (A_{12} + A_{66})u_{,xy} + A_{26}u_{,yy} + A_{66}v_{,xx} + 2A_{26}v_{,xy} + A_{22}v_{,yy} - B_{22}w_{,yyy} = 0 \\ & D_{11}w_{,xxxx} + 4D_{16}w_{,xxxxy} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})w_{,xxxyy} + 4D_{26}w_{,xyyyy} + D_{22}w_{,yyyy} - B_{11}u_{,xxx} - 3B_{16}u_{,xxy} \\ & \quad - (B_{12} + 2B_{66})u_{,xyy} - B_{26}u_{,yyy} - B_{16}v_{,xxx} - (B_{12} + 2B_{66})v_{,xxy} - 3B_{26}v_{,xyy} \\ & \quad - B_{22}v_{,yyy} + N_x w_{,xy} + N_y w_{,yy} + \rho h w_{,tt} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

In the case of symmetrically angle-ply oriented composite plates, $A_{16} = A_{26} = D_{16} = D_{26} = B_{ij} = 0$ and the previous equations simplify. As shown in [7], to solve such equation one can use the separability of space and time with Fourier series in the form: $w(x, y, t) = [\alpha_{mn} \cos(\omega t) + \beta_{mn} \sin(\omega t)] X_m(x) Y_n(y)$ and considering the corresponding boundary conditions, results in a system of equations that will give the natural frequencies and mode shapes, only if a nontrivial solution exists. In this case, for a simple supported plate with edges a and b , the following equation for natural frequencies results:

$$\omega_{m,n}^2 = \frac{\pi^4}{\rho h} [D_{11} \left(\frac{m}{a}\right)^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \left(\frac{m}{a}\right)^2 \left(\frac{n}{b}\right)^2 + D_{22} \left(\frac{n}{b}\right)^4] \quad (11)$$

where m and n are positive integers that should be tried to get each of the mode frequencies.

2.2. Equations for buckling of laminated plates

Assuming that the only applied load are those from in-plane and taking the effects in the total potential energy split into two parts, bending and external forces ($\Pi = U_b + U_p$), one can evaluate those parts for an assumed field solution that accounts for boundary conditions of the form of sine series. In the second example present in this work, the critical buckling load will be evaluated for a clamped plate under uniaxial load. In this case, it is assumed a solution in the form $w(x, y) = w_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/a) \sin(m\pi y/b)$ with w_{mn} being the displacement coefficients and m, n , positive integers. Substituting this and assuming displacement field into the total potential energy, forcing a stationary condition ($\partial \Pi / \partial w_{mn} = 0$) and solving for $\lambda = N_{crit} / N_x$ (critical to the reference applied load ratio), the buckling loads are computed. In fact, the first buckling load is of interest, and one should search for the combinations of m and n that gives the lower λ (first buckling load). In case of a clamped plate with uniaxial load, N_x , the resulting expression is:

$$\lambda_{m,n} = -(G_1 G_5 + G_2 G_4) - \sqrt{(G_1 G_5 + G_2 G_4)^2 - 4(G_2 G_5 - G_3^2) G_1 G_4} / [2(G_2 G_5 - G_3^2)] \quad \text{for } m = 1 | n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (12)$$

$$\lambda_{m,n} = -(H_1 H_5 + H_2 H_4) - \sqrt{(H_1 H_5 + H_2 H_4)^2 - 4(H_2 H_5 - H_3^2) H_1 H_4} / [2(H_2 H_5 - H_3^2)] \quad \text{for } m \neq 1 | \{m, n\} \in \mathbb{N} \quad (13)$$

where

$$G_1 = \pi^4(3D_{11}b^4 + 2D_{12}a^2b^2 + 3D_{22}a^4 + 4D_{66}a^2b^2) / [4a^3b^3] \quad (14)$$

$$G_2 = -\pi^2b(3n^4 - 12n^2) / 16a(n^4 - 4n^2) \quad (15)$$

$$G_3 = 8b(-n^3 + (-1)^{n+2}n^3) / 3a(n^4 - 4n^2) \quad (16)$$

$$G_4 = k\pi^2(A_{44}a^2 + A_{55}n^2b^2) / 4ab \quad (17)$$

$$G_5 = -\pi^2b(n^6 - 4n^4) / 4a(n^4 - 4n^2) \quad (18)$$

$$H_1 = \pi^4(D_{11}b^4(18m^2 + 3 + 3m^4) + D_{12}a^2b^2(8 + 8m^2) + 16D_{22}a^4 + D_{66}a^2b^2(16 + 16m^2)) / (32a^3b^3) \quad (19)$$

$$H_2 = -\pi^2b(3m^6 + 3 + 3n^4 - 3m^4 - 3m^2 + 3m^2n^4 - 12m^2n^2 - 6n^2 - 4m^4n^2) / 32a(1 - 2n^2 + m^4 - 2m^2n^2 - 2m^2 + n^4) \quad (20)$$

$$H_3 = -8b(-mn^3 + (-1)^{m+n+1}mn^3) / 3a(1 - 2n^2 + m^4 - 2m^2n^2 - 2m^2 + n^4) \quad (21)$$

$$H_4 = k\pi^2(A_{44}a^2 + A_{55}n^2b^2) / 4ab \quad (22)$$

$$H_5 = -\pi^2b(n^2 + n^6 - 2m^2n^4 + m^4n^2 - 2n^4 - 2m^2n^2) / 4a(1 - 2n^2 + m^4 - 2m^2n^2 - 2m^2 + n^4) \quad (23)$$

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

3.1. Example 1 - Natural Frequency of a Simply Supported Plate

The following example shows a composite with the total length and breadth of the laminated plate with orthotropic cross-ply $[-45^\circ/45^\circ/0/45^\circ/-45^\circ]$ configuration, dimensions $a=0.3$ m and $b=1.5$ m and laminate thickness of $t=6.25 \times 10^{-4}$ m. The material properties of the laminate are $E_{11}=1.35 \times 10^{11}$ Pa, $E_{22}=8.8 \times 10^9$ Pa, $G_{12}=4.8 \times 10^9$ Pa, $\nu_{12}=0.33$ and $\rho=1380$ kg/m³. The boundary conditions are simply supported on each side (SSSS). In this examples it is assumed an interval uncertainty of $\pm 10\%$, for the worst-case scenario (corresponding to α -cut level 0) in E_{11} , ρ, G_{12} and an uncertainty $\pm 5^\circ$ for θ . This uncertainty is assumed independent for each layer, so the number of uncertainties are 20 in total. The proposed algorithm is tested using the interval approach proposed in this paper and compared with simple MC (Monte Carlo simulations). For fair comparisons, the number of MC simulations equals the number of function calls used in the Interval-based proposed algorithm (that runs first). The uncertainty in the dynamic behavior is sought in this example so, the first four natural frequencies are evaluated. The analytical solutions for the deterministic situation for this particular case are given by Equation (11). The following Figure 3 is obtained for the convex-hulls for the first 4 natural frequencies ($y_1=f_1, y_2=f_2, y_3=f_3$ and $y_4=f_4$ in Hz).

Figure 3 – Output uncertain intervals and convex hulls for the interval-based procedure and MC Simulation for mode frequencies.

Table 1 shows the relative differences between the Interval-based Method (using anti-optimization) proposed here and the traditional Monte Carlo Method based on the Error (E) values defined as the ratio between twice the Interval Radius of the uncertain output variables (first 4 natural frequencies) for the zero α -cut level and the Interval Center. The Interval Radius for an uncertain variable z is defined as $IR = (\bar{z} - \underline{z})/2$, while the Interval Center is defined as $IC = (\bar{z} + \underline{z})/2$, so $E = 2 IR/IC$.

Table 1 – Error-values for interval output variables obtained by the Interval-based Method and the MC method.

Mode Frequency (Hz)	Interval-based Method			MC Method		
	Lowerbound \underline{f}	Upperbound \bar{f}	E (%)	Lowerbound \underline{f}	Upperbound \bar{f}	E (%)
f_1	1.5004×10^1	2.2333×10^1	39.93	1.5804×10^1	2.0971×10^1	28.15
f_2	1.8806×10^1	2.6160×10^1	33.06	1.9722×10^1	2.4784×10^1	22.75
f_3	2.4218×10^1	3.1785×10^1	27.16	2.5310×10^1	3.0403×10^1	18.28
f_4	3.0848×10^1	3.8751×10^1	22.74	3.2159×10^1	3.7523×10^1	15.44

Analyzing Table 1, one can notice the spread of the results obtained with Interval-based Method when compared to the MC method since E values are greater (10% on average). This also can be noticed by the graphs of Figure 3, where the convex hull and interval limits for the Interval-based Method encompass the corresponding values for the MC Method. The numerical evaluations took about 100 seconds in an i9-3.6 GHz computer with 32 GB RAM.

3.2. Example 2 - Buckling Load of a Clamped Plate

The second example is intended to investigate the uncertainty in the first four buckling loads in the case of a clamped plate with a one-dimensional compressive load N_x . In this case, the mass density is not assumed uncertain since it does not collaborate with the buckling load. The material properties are the same as the ones used in example 1. It is assumed the same uncertainty of $\pm 5^\circ$ for θ at each layer and uncertainty of $\pm 10\%$, (for α -cut level 0) in E_{11} , G_{11} and ν_{12} . The dimensions for the plate are $a=0.6$ and $b=0.6$, and the laminate thickness is $t=2.4 \times 10^{-2}$ m with orthotropic cross-ply $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]$. Figure 4 is obtained for the convex-hulls for the first 4 buckling loads, where $y_1=\lambda_1$, $y_2=\lambda_2$, $y_3=\lambda_3$ and $y_4=\lambda_4$ (that are dimensionless).

Figure 4 – Output uncertain intervals and convex hulls for the Interval-based procedure and MC Simulation for buckling loads (dimensionless buckling ratio, $\lambda = N_{crit}/N_x$).

For comparisons purposes, Table 2 shows the differences in for the interval and the simple Monte Carlo results in terms of the Error values.

Table 2 – Error-values for interval output variables obtained by the Interval-based Method and the MC method.

Buckling load ratio	Interval-based Method			MC Method		
	Lower bound $\underline{\lambda}$	Upper bound $\bar{\lambda}$	E (%)	Lower bound $\underline{\lambda}$	Upper bound $\bar{\lambda}$	E (%)
λ_1	1.6730×10^7	2.0287×10^7	19.24	1.6939×10^7	1.9949×10^7	16.28
λ_2	1.7077×10^7	2.0729×10^7	19.34	1.7290×10^7	2.0403×10^7	16.49
λ_3	1.7832×10^7	2.1689×10^7	19.52	1.8098×10^7	2.1355×10^7	16.49
λ_4	1.8143×10^7	2.2099×10^7	19.68	1.8328×10^7	2.1775×10^7	17.15

Again, Analyzing Table 2, one can notice the spread of the results obtained with Interval-based Method when compared to the MC method since E values are greater (3% on average).

4. CONCLUSION

It was observed that the convex hulls as the output intervals are not well-defined when using traditional Monte Carlo Simulation. This is attributed to the fact that the worst scenario is a precise combination of values of uncertain input variables that cannot be obtained by simple random simulations. Despite the huge amount of simulations, the extreme (worst-case scenario) is only correctly defined by the Interval based methodology proposed in this paper. In the examples analyzed, mode frequencies and buckling loads, the Interval based methodology presented 3% to 10% larger error values when compared to the Monte Carlo Method, which implies in a larger uncertain area.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors thank CNPq and CAPES for the partial financial support for this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Hea, L. Liua, A. Makeev. Uncertainty analysis in composite material properties characterization using DIC and finite element model updating. *Comp. Struct.*, 184, (2018), 337-351.
- [2] E. J. Wehrle. Design optimization of lightweight space-frame structures considering crashworthiness and parameter uncertainty. Technical University of Munich. Doctor Dissertation. (2015)
- [3] S. Dey, T. Mukhopadhyay, S. Adhikari. Uncertainty quantification in laminated composites: a meta-model based approach. CRC Press, 2018.
- [4] C.B. Barber, D.P. Dobkin, H. Huhdanpaa. The quickhull algorithm for convex hulls. *ACM Trans Math Soft.* 22(4). (1996), 469–83.
- [5] M. Faes, D. Moens. Identification and quantification of spatial interval uncertainty in numerical models. *Comp. Struct.*, 192, (2017), 16-33.
- [6] S. Dey, T. Mukhopadhyay, S. Adhikari. Stochastic free vibration analysis of angle-ply composite plates – A RS-HDMR approach. *Composite structures* 122 (2015), 526-536.
- [7] Y. Luo, M. Hong, Y. Liu. Analytical solutions to the Fundamental frequency of arbitrary laminated plates under various boundary conditions. *J. of Marine Sc. Appl.* (2015), 14: 46-52.

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